

Recovery of Erosion Prone land by Opiary Implementation

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Montevecchio, Borello, Italy
landslide in the Tosco-Romagnolo Appennine, Multifloral
pasture naturally reestablished over a stabilized

Abandonment and agricultural mechanization of the Mediterranean internal areas have caused profound hydrogeomorphological instability with phenomena of severe soil erosion and landslides. In fact, the ecological fragility of the hilly and mountainous Mediterranean landscapes has been heavily affected in recent decades by the reduced human presence. The depopulation of the internal areas has been accompanied by the degradation of a rural system oriented towards good agroforestry practices and the maintenance of large areas of meadows and pastures. The incipient agricultural mechanization of lands with sloping positions has increased the arable surface area. This, together with the reduced attention to cover crops and hydraulic, agricultural and forestry systems, has caused widespread hydrological instability. Italy is strongly affected by these problems due to the high percentage of territory represented by internal mountain areas. A radical and shared conversion of these rural systems in disarray is now urgent. The recovery of beekeeping can support this conversion towards systems with high biodiversity, rich in permanent crops with arboreal, shrubby and herbaceous components capable of expressing a high melliferous potential. In particular, the numerous areas that have been subject to erosion or landslides, once settled, should be managed exclusively with good agroforestry practices capable of ensuring drainage and stability of the slopes. Here, beekeeping can take advantage of the floristic biodiversity ensured by appropriate protection and greening plantations. For example, a Keyline hydrogeological plan can be accompanied by tree and shrub plantations of melliferous plants while multi-plant meadows with staggered flowering can permanently occupy the watershed areas most exposed to erosion.

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Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No GA 101086563. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.